

FIRM-SPECIFIC ATTRIBUTES AND EARNINGS MANAGEMENT: DOES SIZE REALLY MATTER AS A MODERATING VARIABLE IN NIGERIAN BANKS?**Sunday Olugboye KAJOLA¹, Adekunle ADEYEMI², Abiola Akanbi TONADE³, & Jayeola OLABISI⁴**^{1,4}Department of Accounting Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria²Department of Accounting, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye, Nigeria³Department of Accounting Crescent University, Abeokuta, Nigeria**Abstract**

Financial reports help to bring to the public domain the performance of companies for a given period. Quality financial reports are needed by the various user groups for informed decisions to be made. However, due to asymmetry information between owners and management, there is possibility of corporate management involvement in manipulation of organisations' earnings. This eventually casts doubt in the credibility and reliability of financial reporting system as a tool for investment decision. This study examines the influence of firm attributes on earnings management. It further explores the role of firm size in moderating the effect of each of the four firm attributes on earnings management in ten listed deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2007 to 2018. The dependent variable, earnings management, is measured by discretionary accruals. The independent variable is firm-specific attributes and four proxies- profitability, leverage, age and growth opportunity serve as its indicators. Regression results from pooled ordinary least square show that firm age has a negative, while growth opportunity has a positive and significant, influence on earnings management. Firm size plays a significant moderating role in the relationship between firm age and earnings management. The outcome of this study provides empirical support for Agency theory. Corporate shareholders, regulatory bodies and other stakeholders are advised to take firm age, growth opportunity and size of banks seriously when policy issues on earnings management practices are discussed and corporate governance principles are to be formulated.

Keywords: Agency cost, corporate governance, discretionary accruals, earnings management, firm attributes, Nigeria

JEL Classification: G34, M41, M52

1.0 Introduction

Discourse on earnings management has been a topical issue among academics, regulators/standards setting bodies, investors, shareholders and other stakeholders since the last five decades. The collapse of some giant corporate entities such as Enron, Xerox, Tyco and Nigerian Oceanic Bank (Kajola, 2008), which has been traced to breakdown of corporate governance system, resulting in publication of inappropriate financial reports, helps a lot in making the issue relevant to date.

Financial report is prepared by corporate management, and it explains the performance of an entity to the various user groups (owners/shareholders, investors, capital market regulators,

creditors, government, general public, among others). The report guides the various users in taking informed decisions about the corporate entity. One of the fundamental characteristics which a financial report should have is reliability. If an unreliable report is used to take decision by an investor, the end result can be disastrous as the funds invested may be lost.

Accounting regulatory bodies (local and international) provide different treatments for a number of items in the financial statements. The corporate manager is therefore permitted to use his judgmental discretions in adopting a particular method that suits the organisation. However, some accounting principles have been used indiscriminately by corporate managers by involving in opportunistic behavior through manipulation of financial reports either to enrich themselves at the expense of the owners of the business or to cover their inefficiency while running the affairs of the entity for the reporting period. The manipulation of financial statements, especially in the determination of the income, is affected through the process of “accounting discretionary accrual” or “earnings management”. Earnings management can simply be described as using management efforts in manipulating reported earnings by adopting or changing accounting methods when treating the timing of income and expenses recognition with the aim of misleading the users of the reports. Corporate stakeholders however, cast doubt in the financial reports of organizations that involve in earnings management practices as these reports lack credibility and reliability (Uwuigbe, Uwuigbe & Okorie, 2015). The investors’ confidence in utilizing the financial report as decision making tool has greatly been reduced (Ogoun & Perelayefa, 2020).

Corporate investors and other stakeholders appreciate a financial report that is of high quality as it enhances the level of transparency, reliability and makes possible informed and better decision to be taken. It also reduces asymmetry information between the management and user groups, to the barest minimum (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

Firm-specific attributes play a pivotal role in explaining quality of earnings to both internal and external stakeholders and can be used to curtail earnings management practices of corporate managers (Mutende, Mwangi & Ochieng, 2017). Corporate entities have different attributes such as, age, leverage, size, profitability, ownership structure, liquidity and others. Prior studies have documented that these various attributes have influence on the practice of earnings management. However, most of these studies (DeAngelo, 1981, Hope, Thomas and Vyas, 2013, Parte-Esteban and Garcia, 2014) were conducted in the developed countries and findings were mixed.

In Nigeria, despite various corporate governance codes that have been issued so far by the regulatory agencies- Central Bank of Nigeria, CBN (2014, 2018), Securities and Exchange Commission, SEC (2003, 2011, 2018) and Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria, FRC (2018), earnings management practices, especially in the banking sector, still persists. Empirical studies which should explain the reason(s) for this are also limited thereby creating a huge knowledge gap.

In the few studies conducted in Nigeria, attempts were made in investigating the influence of one or two firm-specific characteristics on earnings management. For instance, Obigbemi, Iyoha, and Ojeka (2015) examined firm size and financial performance, Okafor, Ezeagba, and Onyali (2018) focused on financial performance, and Kwarbai, Akintoye, Adegbei and Nwaobia (2019) considered only growth opportunity as firm-specific variables. Furthermore, none of the Nigerian studies, so far, has considered the moderating role of a firm variable on other variables in explaining the relationship between variables and earnings management.

This study, therefore, tries to bridge the gap noticed in some prior empirical studies by having the objective of exploring the effect of four firm-specific characteristics (age, leverage, profitability, and growth opportunity) on earnings management in the Nigerian banking sector. Firm size is further used as a moderating variable to test relationship that exists between the four firm-specific variables and earnings management.

The subsequent part of this paper covers the literature review, methodology, which sets out the specific model, measurement of variables and analytical tool adopted, discussion of empirical results and conclusion of the study.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Earnings Management

Earnings management involves institutional manipulation of financial information with the aim of communicating biased reports to the various users of the information. It is generally agreed that earnings management is within the framework of Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) and therefore is not an illegal act (Bassiouny, Soliman & Ragab, 2016). It is also pertinent to note that a financial report, with extreme form of earnings management, contains inaccurate and unreliable information about the economic performance of the entity and this can impair the confidence in its use if eventually detected by investors and other stakeholders (Ogoun & Perelayefa, 2020).

Earnings management can be perpetrated in many ways. One of such is based on accruals. In this way, accrued revenue from sales or closing inventories can be manipulated either by increasing or reducing the value in the reported financial period to achieve a planned objective of the management. Another technique of earnings management is based on real transaction, and it involves structuring of actual activities of the entity's business and time (Ali, Noor, Khurshid & Mahmood, 2015).

There are some reasons advanced to support corporate managers' involvement in this unethical behaviour. Firstly, managers use their control over the firm to participate in earnings management practices in order to derive personal benefits at expense of owners of the business (Prior, Surroca & Tribo, 2008, Uwuigbe, 2013). They also use the opportunity to cover their inefficiency in running the affair of the businesses so as to prevent loss of office or possible take-over by other well-managed organisations. Whatever the reason for management

involvement in earnings manipulation, most countries' institutional and regulatory bodies frown at it. Hence, many codes of corporate governance have been issued to mitigate this unethical practice.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Agency theory best provides theoretical explanation to the interaction between corporate governance attributes and earnings management. Agency problem, according to Jensen and Meckling (1976), occurs as a result of separation of ownership and control in an organisation. In this situation, the management (agents) may resort to some actions that will profit them as managers, but which are inconsistent with the expectations of the owners (principal). Relating to earnings management, corporate managers may decide to choose accrual accounting basis, which is easier to manipulate, over the cash flow basis accounting when corporate transactions are reported in the financial statements (Chen, Kong & Wang, 2014). Further, discretionary accrual, which is part of total accruals, can easily be manipulated as it is within the control of the management. This will make it easily possible for managers to determine the timing of revenue earned and recognition of expenses incurred. The bottom line is that inaccurate and misleading reports will be communicated to the various user groups when earnings management practice takes place.

2.3 Firm-specific Attributes and Development of Hypotheses

2.3.1 Age of Firm and Earnings Management

Experience comes with age, hence the older the firm, the better will every aspect of the entity's activity be. The operational cost will be greatly reduced while quality services are provided. The reporting system of an older firm would have improved over time (Alsaeed, 2006). Older firms also have reputation and goodwill to protect. As a result of this, it is proposed that the older a firm is, the lower will be tendency for its managers to involve in earnings manipulation. The empirical results on the relationship between the two variables, is however mixed.

Pranesh and Chinmoy (2017) evaluated the impact of five firm characteristics on earnings management in India and the regression result showed that older firms have the greater tendency to manipulate their earnings. The studies conducted by Jackson, Rountre and Weston (2013) and Khanh and Nguyen (2018) revealed a negative and significant relationship between firm age and earnings management. Bassiouny *et al.* (2015) study of Egyptian non-financial firms indicated a negative and insignificant relationship. In the light of the foregoing mixed findings, this study postulates the first hypothesis as:

H₁: Age has significant influence on earnings management of Nigerian deposit money banks.

2.3.2 Leverage and Earnings Management

Debt is a major source of finance for any organisation that intends to invest in viable projects or for expansion of operations. But this source comes with a cost, which must be dealt with in accordance with the debt covenant imposed by the lender. Prior studies suggest that managers

tend to choose the accounting methods that increase reporting earnings but the scrutiny of the financial statements by the lenders make it difficult for the firm to involve in abnormal earnings management (Jensen, 1986).

Olaoye and Adewumi (2018) assessed the interaction between corporate governance and earnings management in Nigerian banks during financial years, 2006-2015. Regression result suggested a negative and significant relationship between leverage and earnings management. Aries (2015) used a sample of thirty manufacturing companies in Indonesia to assess the influence of leverage and size on earnings management for financial years, 2009-2013. Regression results suggested that the two proxies of financial leverage, operating leverage and financial leverage had negative but insignificant association with earnings management. Salah (2018) examined the effect of firm characteristics on earnings quality in 45 Egyptian listed industrial firms for the period 2014-2017. Result from pooled ordinary least square (OLS) regression indicated a positive and significant relationship between firm leverage and earnings management. Same findings were obtained in studies conducted in France by Lazzem and Jilani (2018) and in the United Kingdom by Anagnostopoulou and Tsekrekos (2017). Consistent with the prior studies as reviewed, this study develops the second hypothesis.

H₂: Leverage has significant influence on earnings management of Nigerian deposit money banks.

2.3.3 Profitability and Earnings Management

Profitability is a major objective of any business entity. A firm that makes consistent profits over time will attract interest of skilled personnel, potential investors and access to cheaper funds in the capital market. Owners of businesses also use profitability as a measure of evaluating the performance of corporate boards. Astami and Tower (2006) submitted that profitability has been used in compensation contracts both explicitly and implicitly. Corporate managers may likely involve in earnings management practices by “smoothing” accruals in a way where reporting earnings will be increased when business activities slow down (Sweeney, 1998). When managers are entitled to bonus compensation that is performance-based, the tendency for managers to choose accounting policies that will bring future earnings to current period in order to have “increased reported earnings” will be high.

Dabor and Ibadin (2013) investigated the factors that determine earnings management in the banking sector of Nigeria for the period 2005-2010. Using Pearson correlation matrix as analytical tool, the result revealed a positive association between firm profitability and earnings management. Some other studies such as Oosterbosch (2009) and Salah (2018) also observed positive association in their studies. Pranesh (2017) study of 84 non-financial companies over 9-year period (2007-2015) suggested a weak negative association (at 10% level of significance) between financial performance and earnings management. Alhadab and Al-own (2017) conducted a unique study on the effect of earnings management on current and future financial performance of 477 bank-year observations in 55 European countries over 2001-2015 financial

years. Regression results indicated a negative relation between current year financial performance proxies and earnings management and this situation feeds through the following year. Tabassum, Kaleem and Nazir (2013) and Hosseinian and Ramzani (2016) also reported a negative and significant relationship between the two variables in prior studies conducted. Atu, Atu, Enegebe and Atu (2016) assessed the determinants of earnings management in 30 listed firms in Nigeria for the period 2007-2014. The OLS regression results indicated no significant relationship. Okafor *et al.*, (2018) and Ubesie, Nwankwo and Nwankwo. (2020) also reported similar results in their studies. Based on the mixed results from prior studies, the third hypothesis is hereby postulated thus:

H₃: Profitability has significant influence on earnings management of Nigerian deposit money banks.

2.3.4 Growth Opportunity and Earnings Management

Growth opportunity is an important internal control feature that has the tendency to be used directly or indirectly by managers to involve in opportunistic behaviour such as earnings management. The information asymmetry hypothesis best explains the interaction between growth opportunity and earnings management. It proposes that information asymmetry could be larger for firms with more growth potentials (than firms with more assets-in-place) as it will cost higher to monitor such firms (Skinner, 1993, Kwarbai *et al.*, 2019).

Gorganlidavaji and Vakilifard (2014) investigated the association between size, growth opportunity and earnings management and its effects on stock return of 125 Iranian listed companies for the period 2002-2012. Regression result suggests firm's growth and earnings management are negatively related. In contrast to this finding, Pranesh (2017), using dataset from non-financial companies in India during 2007-2015 revealed a positive association between firm growth and earnings management. Kwarbai *et al.*, (2019) examined the growth opportunity-earnings quality nexus of 26 companies in Nigeria for the period 1996-2016. The result of the regression analysis indicated a positive association between the two variables.

As a result of the mixed outcomes from various studies reviewed, we propose the fourth hypothesis as:

H₄: Firm growth opportunity has significant influence on earnings management of Nigerian deposit money banks.

2.3.5 Firm size, Earnings Management and its Moderating Role

Firm size is one of the effective internal control mechanisms of a business entity. Large firms attract some benefits (than small firms), such as easy access to funds from the capital market, production of quality items at cheaper cost due to economy of scale, experienced personnel, especially in accounting and internal audit functions, goodwill and reputation. They also have the funds required to engage the services of big audit firms. It is, therefore, expected that the financial report produce by a large firm will be free from major earnings manipulation compared to a small firm (Ahmad, Anjum & Azeem, 2014, Ali *et al.* 2015). The corporate internal audit

unit, with experienced accounting professionals would have done a great job in carrying out its mandate of putting in place effective internal control system and this will impact on its ability to detect earnings management quickly and effectively. The external audit firm aims at protecting its reputation by diligently scrutinize the financial reports presented by management as its inability to detect a material defect in the report may cast doubt in audit firm's professional competencies. This suggests an indirect association between firm size and earnings management (Paiva & Lourenco, 2010, Lusi & Swastika, 2013).

There are some other views that are not consistent with the negative relation. Agency theory proposes that large firms incur greater agency costs than small firms and this leads to more opportunistic behaviour on the part of large-sized managers (Jensen, 1986, Hassan & Farouk, 2014). Also, the need to meet the pressure from investment analysts can make corporate managers to involve in earnings management practices (Bassiouny *et al.*, 2016).

Uwuigbe *et al.*, (2015) assessed the influence of three firm-specific variables (corporate strategy, firm size and leverage) on earnings management in twenty Nigerian quoted firms for the financial years, 2006-2010. Findings from the pooled OLS regression revealed that firm size exhibits positive and significant effect on earnings management. Ali *et al.*, (2015) explored the association between firm size and earnings management of fifty Pakistani textile firms for the period, 2004-2013. The regression result revealed a positive association between the two variables. Bassiouny *et al.*, (2016) investigated the influence of firm characteristics on earnings management of sixty listed non-financial firms in Egypt during the period covering 2007-2011. The result of the random effect generalised least square regression indicated an insignificant relationship.

Agency theory supports the view that firm size has the capacity to affect the impact of other firm-specific variables on earnings management. This is because larger firms have higher agency problems than smaller firms thereby creating avenue for corporate managers to use other firm-specific variables in conjunction with the moderating role of firm size to “smoothing” the financial reports so as to achieve an intended purpose.

Thus, with the introduction of firm size as a moderating variable, the following ancillary hypotheses are constructed:

H_{1A}: Firm size has a significant moderating effect in the relationship between age and earnings management of Nigerian deposit money banks.

H_{2A}: Firm size has a significant moderating effect in the relationship between leverage and earnings management of Nigerian deposit money banks.

H_{3A}: Firm size has a significant moderating effect in the relationship between profitability and earnings management of Nigerian deposit money banks.

H_{4A}: Firm size has a significant moderating effect in the relationship between growth opportunity and earnings management of Nigerian deposit money banks.

The conceptual model of the study is as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

Source: Authors’ conceptualisation (2020)

From the Figure 1, the four firm- specific variables are proposed to have direct linkage with the independent variable, earnings management. This linkage results in the testing of hypotheses 1, 2, 3 and 4. With firm size as a moderating variable, there is an indirect linkage from firm size, which intercepts each of the lines that link the firm-specific variables to the earnings management. This situation enables the study to test hypotheses 1A, 2A, 3A and 4A.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Data source

Data were obtained from secondary source only. Relevant information on firm-specific variables and earnings management were gotten from published annual reports of the sample banks as well as from the database of Nigerian stock exchange Factbook for the period of study, 2007-2018.

3.2 Population and sample

Nigeria has a total population of fifteen listed deposit money banks as at the financial year end of 2018. To achieve the objective of the study, ten firms, which represents about 67% of the population, was purposeful selected as sample for the study. The sample banks cut across the three classes (regional, national and international) of banks in Nigeria. The list of the sample banks is provided in Appendix A.

3.3 Model specification

Consistent with some prior studies (Salah, 2018, Soyemi, Olufemi & Adeyemi, 2020; Hajawiyah, Wahyudin, Sakinah & Pahala, 2020), there exist a functional relation between the dependent (earnings management) and explanatory variables (firm-specific attributes and control variables) and is as presented in equation 1.

$$EMT = f(FAG, FLV, PRF, GOP, BOS, BOC) \quad (1)$$

The study has two specific objectives. The first objective examines the linkage between the four firm-specific variables and EMT, while in the second objective; the moderating role of firm size in the relationship between the four firm-specific variables and earnings management is explored. The two objectives are captured in the econometric model presented in equation 2.

$$EMT_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1FAG_{it} + \beta_2FLV_{it} + \beta_3PRF_{it} + \beta_4GOP_{it} + \beta_5BOS_{it} + \beta_6BOC_{it} + \beta_7FAG*FSZ_{it} + \beta_8FLV*FSZ_{it} + \beta_9PRF*FSZ_{it} + \beta_{10}GOP*FSZ_{it} + \beta_{11}BOS*FSZ_{it} + \beta_{12}BOC*FSZ_{it} + e_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where: EMT - Earnings management; FAG - Firm age; FLV - Firm leverage; PRF - Profitability; GOP - Growth opportunity; BOS - Board size; BCO - Board composition, FSZ - Firm size; $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{12}$ Variable parameters; e - Error term

Variable description and measurement

Dependent variable

Earnings management is the dependent variable. Like in some prior studies (Jung, Kim and Chung, 2016 and Echobu, Okika and Mailafia, 2017), Discretionary Accruals (DA), as provided in modified Jones (1991) model is adopted as a surrogate for measuring earnings management. The DA method, according to Dechow, Sloan and Sweeney (1995), Muhammed and Ibrahim (2018) and Soyemi, *et. al.*, (2020), is considered as the most commonly used and best approach in measuring earnings management.

Accruals can be calculated through Balance sheet and cash flow statement approaches. However, the cash flow approach has been acclaimed in recent empirical literature as the most efficient method in estimating accruals (Agrawal & Chatterjee, 2015, Ajay & Madhumathi, 2015, Pradesh, 2017). The current study therefore follows the cash flow statement approach in estimating accruals.

There are some steps to be taken in computing the value of earnings management proxy by DA. The first step requires the determination of Total Accruals (TA) and this is as stated in equation 3.

$$TA_t = NI_t - CFO_t \quad (3)$$

Where: TA_t = Total accruals in year t; NI_t = Net income in year t; CFO_t = Cash flow from operating activities in year t

TA comprises the Discretionary Accruals (DA) and Non-Discretionary Accruals (NDA). With the use of modified Jones (1991) model as cited by Bassiouny *et al* (2016) and Pradesh (2017), NDA is derived. This is as specified in equation 4.

$$NDA_t = \beta_{1j} \{1/T_{it-1}\} + \beta_{2j} \{(\Delta RVN_t - \Delta RCV)/T_{it-1}\} + \beta_{3j} \{PPE_i/T_{i-1}\} \quad (4)$$

Where: T_{it-1} - Total assets for firm j lagged by one year; ΔRVN - Change in revenue for firm j in year t less revenue in year $t - 1$; ΔRCV - Change in receivables for firm j in year t less receivables in year $t - 1$; PPE - Property, plant and equipment for firm j in year t ; β_{1j} β_{2j} β_{3j} Firm-specific parameters

The next step is to find the parameters of the firm variables necessary in the formulation of NDA equation. This is exhibited in form of regression equation as reported in equation 5 (Salleh &Haat, 2014, Uwuigbeet *al.*, 2015, Pranesh, 2017).

$$\frac{TA_t}{T_{it-1}} = \beta_{1j} \{1/T_{it-1}\} + \beta_{2j} \{(\Delta RVN_t - \Delta RCV)/T_{it-1}\} + \beta_{3j} \{PPE_i/T_{i-1}\} + e_{it} \quad (5)$$

Since both the TA and NDA values are known, then the DA can be computed by subtracting the value of NDA from TA as presented in equation 6 as a guide (Salleh &Haat, 2014, Uwuigbe, *et. al.*, 2015, Pranesh, 2017).

$$DA_{jt} = \frac{TA}{T_{it-1}} - NDA_{jt} \quad (6)$$

Independent variables

Based on the review of relevant literature, the study considers four firm-specific variables (firm age, leverage, profitability, and growth opportunity) that are capable of influencing earnings management in Nigerian banking system, as independent variables.

Control variables

Apart from firm-specific attributes that may have influence on earnings management practices, there are some other corporate governance factors capable of doing same but which are not captured in our model. The study adopts two of such factors- board size and board composition, as control variables.

Moderating variable

Size of a firm, according to Agency theory, is a potent mechanism that is capable of moderating the effect of each of the firm-specific variables on earnings management, hence its adoption in this study as a moderating variable.

The measurement of other variables is depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Measurement of other variables

Variable	Measure	Studies
Firm age (FAG)	Natural log of the years since incorporation to the year of study	Bassiouny <i>et al.</i> , (2016), Pranesh and Chinmoy (2017), Salah (2018),

Leverage (FLV)	$\frac{\text{Total debts}}{\text{Total assets}}$	Samad (2015), Bassiounyet <i>al.</i> , (2016), Hajawiyahet <i>al.</i> , (2020),
Profitability (PRF)	$\frac{\text{Net income}}{\text{Total assets}}$	Yuksel, Mukhtarov, Mammadov and Osari (2018), Efuntade and Akinola (2020)
Growth opportunity (GOP)	$\frac{\text{Deposits}_t - \text{Deposits}_{t-1}}{\text{Deposits}_{t-1}}$	Kajola, Olabisi, Ajayi and Agbatogun (2018)
Board size (BOS)	Number of directors in the boardroom	Dabor and Dabor (2015), Abata and Migiroy (2016),
Board composition (BCO)	Ratio of number of external directors to total directors in the boardroom	Akintayo and Salman (2018), Uwuigbe, Eluyela, Uwuigbe, Obarakpo and Falola (2018), Shubita (2020)
Firm size (FSZ)	Natural log of total assets	Ali <i>et al.</i> , (2015), Kajola <i>et al.</i> , (2018)

Source: Authors' compilation

Data estimation technique

The study is in form of panel methodology. Two different analytical tools- pooled OLS and Fixed effect least square (FEM) were employed. The Wald test was later conducted to discriminate between pooled OLS and FEM. The result supports the use of pooled OLS as a better analytical technique for purpose of making inference.

4.0 Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistics

Table 2 presents the summary of descriptive statistics. The average earnings management (EMT) is 0.151, with minimum of 0.001 and maximum of 0.901. The mean bank size (FSZ) of N1,183 billion (that is, log inverse 12.073), with minimum of N130 billion (log inverse 11.113) and maximum of N8,318 billion (log inverse 12.920). The mean age of the sampled banks is about 33 years (log inverse 1.513). Bank leverage (FLV) has an average of 0.076, suggesting that the ratio of debt to total asset, on the average, is 7.6%. This implies that the banks are lowly geared. Average profitability (PRF) is 1.1%, indicating that there is poor return on the assets of the banks. Growth opportunity has a mean of 22.3%. Average size of the board (BOS) is about 14, while the proportion of non-executive directors sitting in boardroom is 63.2%. This is consistent with the provisions of SEC (2011) code, which suggests that boards of listed companies should comprise more of non-executive/independent directors than executive directors. BOS with standard deviation of 2.875 is the variable with the highest variability from mean, while PRF with standard deviation of 0.045 has the least variability.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation
EMT	.151	.001	.901	.198
FSZ	12.073	11.113	12.920	.403

FAG	1.513	.301	2.097	.337
FLV	.076	.000	.684	.081
PRF	.011	-.296	.106	.045
GOP	.223	-.325	1.674	.317
BOS	13.567	6.000	20.000	2.875
BOC	.632	.462	.900	.106

Source: Authors' computation (2020)

Correlation

Table 3 presents the Pearson correlation matrix of the study variables. The association between earnings management (EMT) and firm size (FSZ) is negative and significant at 1% level. Firm age (FAG) has a negative association with EMT at 5% level. Growth opportunity (GOP) however has a direct association with EMT at 5% level. The association between remaining variables- profitability, board size, board composition and EMT is insignificant.

Correlation matrix also helps in investigating the presence of collinearity problem among the series. A variable is said to have a multicollinearity issue if its coefficient is greater than 0.8 (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). There is no variable in Table 3 that has a coefficient of at least 0.8; the highest being -0.660 (association between board size and board composition). Thus, the series have no multicollinearity problem.

Collinearity

Tolerance Value (TV) and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) approaches were further employed to validate existence or otherwise of multicollinearity issue among the series used in the study. Table 4 presents the result of multicollinearity test.

Table 3: Correlation matrix

	EMT	FSZ	FAG	FLV	PRF	GOP	BOS	BOC
EMT	1							
FSZ	-.238*** (.004)	1						
FAG	-.188** (.020)	.318*** (.000)	1					
FLV	-.206** (.012)	-.103 (.132)	.096 (.148)	1				
PRF	.111 (.114)	.284*** (.001)	-.125 (.087)	-.180** (.025)	1			
GOP	.549*** (.000)	-.236*** (.005)	-.218** * (.008)	-.273*** (.001)	.061 (.254)	1		
BOS	-.057	.253***	.003	-.243***	.211**	.002	1	

	(.268)	(.003)	(.487)	(.004)	(.010)	(.489)	
BOC	-.079	-.064	.185**	-.007	-.179**	-.087	-.660*** 1
	(.195)	(.243)	(.021)	(.472)	(.025)	(.172)	(.000)

* p<10%; ** p <5%; *** p <1%,

Source: Authors’ computation (2020)

Table 4: Collinearity test result

Variable	TV	VIF
FAG	.789	1.267
FLV	.771	1.296
PRF	.835	1.198
GOP	.824	1.214
BOS	.454	2.201
BOC	.480	2.082
FSZ	.715	1.398

Source: Authors’ computation (2020)

Regression Results

Table 5 presents the results of the regression analysis based on pooled OLS technique. According to the Table , R² is 0.425974, which suggests that about 43% of the variation in earnings management is explained by the explanatory, control and intervening variables, while about 57% is due to other factors not included in the model. The adjusted R² is about 37%, while the F-stat is 5.113343 and this is significant at 1% level (p = 0.0000). This reveals that the model is properly fitted. The Durbin-Watson stat of 1.5747 suggests absence of serial autocorrelation in the model (Alsaed, 2006, Kajola, Olabisi & Fapetu, 2019).

FAG has a negative and significant relationship with EMT at 1% level (p < 0.01). It suggests that as a bank gets older, the tendency for corporate management’s involvement in manipulation of financial reporting system reduces. This finding agrees with the studies by Jackson *et al.*, (2013) and Khanh and Nguyen (2018). It is however not in line with studies conducted by Bassiounyet al., (2016) and Salah (2018) that produced insignificant results between the two variables. Hypothesis 1 is hereby confirmed. Thus, firm age has significant influence on earnings management in Nigerian banks. The influence of moderating variable, firm size, on the relationship between firm age (FAG*FSZ) and EMT shows a positive and significant relationship at 1% level. It implies that firm size has a significant interaction effect between firm age and earnings management. However, the moderating role of firm size results in positive impact of firm age on EMT. The outcome of the study supports hypothesis 1A. Thus, firm size moderates the effect of firm age on earnings management in Nigerian banks.

The relationship between leverage (FLV) and EMT is positive but insignificant at 5% level (p > 0.05). It indicates that firm leverage is not a potent governance mechanism that could be used by

shareholders in monitoring the activities of corporate management in curtailing earnings management practices. This finding is consistent with the study by Aries (2015). It is however not in line with the studies conducted by Anagnostopoulou and Tsekrekos (2017) and Salah (2018), which produced positive and significant relationship. Hypothesis 2 is hereby rejected. Thus, firm leverage has no significant influence on EMT in Nigerian banks. Regression result also reveals an insignificant effect in the role of firm size on the association between firm leverage (FLV*FSZ) and EMT. Hypothesis 2A is rejected. Thus, firm size does not moderate the effect of firm leverage on earnings management in Nigerian banks.

Profitability (PRF) has a negative but insignificant relationship with earnings management ($p > 0.05$). The outcome supports the studies by (2016), Okafor *et al.*, (2018) and Ubesie *et al.*, (2020). It is however contrary to the studies by Dabor and Ibadin (2013) and Salah (2018), which produced positive and significant relationship. Hypothesis 3 is hereby rejected. As for the moderating role of firm size in the relationship between profitability (PRF*FSZ) and EMT, regression result shows positive and insignificant relationship. This indicates that firm size has no significant interaction in the profitability-EMT nexus. Hypothesis 3A is rejected.

Growth opportunity (GOP) and EMT are directly related and significant at 5% level ($p < 0.05$). It implies that as the banks become larger and evolving from increase in information asymmetry. The corporate managers have the impetus to increase earnings management practices. Finding has the support of studies by Pranesh (2017) and Kwarbai *et al.*, (2019). It is however contrary to the studies by Gorganlidavaji and Vakilifard (2014) and Anton and Carp (2020), which produced negative and significant relationship between the two variables. Hypothesis 4 is validated. On the intervening effect of firm size in the relationship between growth opportunity (GOP*FSZ) and EMT, the regression result indicates a negative and insignificant relationship at 5% level ($p > 0.05$). It therefore shows that firm size did not have impact in the relationship between growth opportunity and earnings management. Hypothesis 4A is not supported by our finding.

Regarding the influence of the control variables, board size (BOS) and board composition (BOC), on EMT, regression results show mixed outcome. BOS has a positive and significant relationship with EMT. It indicates that as board size increases, the tendency for corporate managers' involvement in earnings management practices increases. This validates theoretical expectation which proposes that it will be difficult for effective coordination of board activities when the size of the board is larger, thereby enabling earnings management practices to continue unhindered. The finding is supported by the study by Santiago and Brown (2009). BOC has positive and insignificant relationship with EMT. This provides support for studies by Mominah (2017) and Shiyanbola, Ogbemor, Okeke, and Okunade, (2019). The regression results further indicate the importance of firm size as a moderating variable in the relationship between board size and EMT as result shows negative and significant relationship at 1% level. However, firm size has no influence, as a moderating variable, in the relationship between board composition and earnings management, as result produced negative and insignificant relationship.

Table 5: Regression Results

Variable	Coefficien t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FAG	-3.91536	1.325851	-2.953092***	0.0039
FLV	3.342972	4.334996	0.771159	0.4423
PRF	-14.4097	9.581391	-1.503925	0.1355
GOP	3.348447	1.645773	2.034574**	0.0443
FAG*FSZ	0.333021	0.112139	2.969729***	0.0037
FLV*FSZ	-0.2775	0.373442	-0.743079	0.4590
PRF*FSZ	1.259398	0.818745	1.538205	0.1269
GOP*FSZ	-0.25781	0.139311	-1.850645*	0.0670
BOS*FSZ	-0.03134	0.010639	-2.945715***	0.0039
BOC*FSZ	-0.26015	0.281154	-0.925302	0.3569
BOS	0.381789	0.129446	2.949401***	0.0039
BOC	2.921714	3.373543	0.866067	0.3884
R ²	.425974	Mean dependent var		.151033
Adjusted R ²	.367508	S.D. dependent var		.197912
S.E. of regression	.157398	Akaike info criterion		-.76544
Sum squared resid	2.675607	Schwarz criterion		-.48669
Log likelihood	57.92631	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-.65224
	5.113343			1.57472
F-stat (prob)	0.0000		Durbin-Watson	5

* p<10%; ** p <5%; *** p <1%,

Source: Authors' computation (2020)

5.0 Conclusion

This study examined the influence of four firm-specific factors (age, leverage, profitability and growth opportunity) on earnings management. To address the knowledge gap noticed in most Nigerian empirical studies, the current study further explored the moderating role of firm size in the relationship between each of the four firm-specific factors and earnings management using data from ten deposit money banks for the period 2007-2018. Earnings management was surrogated by Discretionary accruals (DA).

Result of pooled OLS technique revealed an indirect and significant influence of firm age on earnings management, while growth opportunity exhibited a positive and significant relationship. In assessing moderating role of firm size in the relationship between the firm-specific variables and earnings management, regression result showed that firm size only played significant moderating role in the relationship between firm age and earnings management. The outcome of this study empirically supports Agency theory.

It is recommended that shareholders, financial analysts, investors and regulatory bodies should take note of the importance of firm size, age and growth opportunity when issues of earnings management are being considered and corporate governance principles formulated.

The study makes additional empirical contribution to the corporate governance literature by revealing the importance of firm size as a potent corporate governance variable in the relationship between firm age and earnings management in the banking sector of an emerging economy, like Nigeria.

In the future, attempt should be made by researchers to consider more firm-specific factors and sample size. Other alternative measurements of earnings management should be explored. There is also the need to replicate this study in other economic sectors and countries.

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APPENDIX A- List of sample banks

S/N	Name
1	Access Bank Plc
2	FCMB Plc
3	Fidelity Bank Plc
4	First Bank Plc
5	GTBankPlc
6	Sterling Bank Plc
7	Wema Bank Plc
8	UBA Plc
9	Union Bank Plc
10	Zenith Bank Plc